

KAPPAHL 2016

ANNUAL REPORT PART I | OPERATIONS | SUSTAINABILITY | EARNINGS

*"Clear concepts and
inspiring shopping
experiences are
the way forward"*

KappAhl

KAPPAHL WAS FOUNDED IN 1953 in Gothenburg and is now one of the leading Nordic fashion chains with 400 stores in Sweden, Norway, Finland and Poland as well as Shop Online.

WE OFFER VALUE FOR MONEY FASHION of our own design with wide appeal – to women, men and children, with special focus on inspiring and guiding women in the prime of life. 38 per cent of the range has sustainable fashion labelling and our ambition is to increase this every year.

IN 2015/2016 NET SALES were SEK 4.7 billion and the number of employees was about 4,000 in nine countries. KappAhl has been listed on Nasdaq Stockholm since 2006.

THIS IS KAPPAHL

KappAhl is a fully integrated fashion chain that offers a good value range of our own design.

OUR VALUE CHAIN

We work to create profitable and sustainable operations throughout our value chain.

OUR CUSTOMER

We always have our customer in mind and we work to create fashion that makes her feel good.

CONTENTS

Our customer	8	Our value chain	18	This is KappAhl	44
President/CEO on the past year	10	Design and purchasing	20	Figures in summary	51
Employees	14	Production	26	Annual General Meeting	52
		Logistics	34	Calendar	52
		Sales	36		
		Consumption	42		

ABOUT THE ANNUAL REPORT

THIS IS KAPPAHL'S ANNUAL REPORT for the period September 2015 to August 2016, part I. The previous report was published on 4 November 2015 this part of the annual report presents the company, our customers and the year's work, earnings and future focus on the basis of material challenges and opportunities. Part 2 of the annual report can be found at kappahl.com/ir. It contains the formal annual accounts, the GRI Index, materiality analysis, our corporate governance report and a multi-year review and extended share information. The sustainability report in the annual report covers Global Reporting Initiatives (GRI) guidelines for reporting in the G4 Core sustainability area. The selection is based on our sustainability strategy and materiality analysis. Information on sustainability presented in the annual report has not been externally assured. Ethos International, a consultancy specialising in sustainability, has assisted KappAhl in updating the materiality analysis to define material aspects for 2015/2016 and ensuring that the content of the report follows the GRI G4 core level guidelines.

This report is an unofficial translation of the corresponding Swedish document. In the event of any discrepancies between the text contained in this document and the Swedish document, the latter shall prevail.

KAPPAHL IN FIGURES 2015/2016

Sales SEK 4,724 (4,588) million

Gross margin 61.8 (60.1) %

Operating margin 7.4 (4.3) %

Earnings per share after dilution SEK 3.19 (1.45)

4,047 employees

38 % sustainable fashion labelling

12 new stores, of which three Newbie Stores and two Hampton Republic 27 stores

298 inspections and follow-up visits at our suppliers

128 tonnes of textiles collected in our textile collecting

At KappAhl **our purpose** is to create a better everyday life for the woman in the prime of life, and her family, through offering a wide range of well-designed and feel good fashion, always in a sustainable way.

TIMELESS FASHION

Black trousers with a good fit that retain their blackness wash after wash. A white shirt. A V-neck pullover. A dress that works for both party and workday. Garments with a design that lasts and that hold your wardrobe together. Season after season. At KappAhl we call it Timeless Fashion. This is a wardrobe consisting of garments that you particularly enjoy wearing, that are simple to vary and complement and that suit any occasion.

CLASSICS IN A SPORTY PREPPY STYLE

At Hampton Republic 27 you find classics in a sporty preppy style. Attractive and comfortable sweaters, blazers, shirts, t-shirts, tennis shirts and chinos. "Always look great, no matter the occasion" is the implicit dress code at Hampton Republic 27. The inspiration is from the good life of the trendsetting holiday resort, The Hamptons, on Route 27, a few hours' drive from New York. The concept has grown strong among KappAhl's customers in recent years and moved from just menswear to also including womenswear and kidswear. During the year KappAhl also opened the two first stand-alone Hampton Republic 27 stores, in Stockholm and Gothenburg.

STURDY OUTERWEAR FOR STURDY KIDS

With outerwear from Kaxs, playful kids stay warm and dry whatever the weather. Kaxs Proxtex is the outerwear series with garments that all have taped seams and a rating of 10,000 in a hydrostatic head test. The garments are designed to be convenient for everyday wear and are easy to put on and take off. They fit well and are manufactured from high quality material.

Kaxs was a success right from the start in 2008 and was produced to meet customer demand. The unisex collection is characterised by strong colours, graphic prints and "mix and match".

FASHION THAT FEELS RIGHT FOR YOU

WE WANT TO STRENGTHEN WOMEN'S SELF IMAGE. We want women to feel good in themselves. And we are driven by the conviction that when you feel good, you look good.

We know our customer well. She likes clothes and wants to feel attractive and feminine. But also comfortable. So we work on fit and offer clothes in many sizes. We honour diversity of shapes and work very hard to create a flattering cut for different body types.

Our customer thinks clothes are fun. But styling and matching are not always that simple. Our skilled employees, with their feeling for style and knowledge of our range, can inspire and guide the customer towards the right choice. Both as regards the fit of clothes and suggestions for suitable accessories.

Our customer wants a warm reception and value-for-money clothes. It must be easy to find what she is looking for. Both in store and online. Both when she is shopping for herself and when she is shopping from the men's and the kid's departments.

It is also important to our customer that the clothes are sustainably produced. We offer more sustainable materials and work constantly to improve our supply chain and create good working conditions at our suppliers. We endeavour to reduce our climate impact and inspire our customer to take good care of clothes and donate garments they have stopped wearing to our textile collecting.

When all the pieces fall into place it feels right. Fashion is a feeling. We help our customer find it.

It is time that fashion makes you feel.

What if we always realised how beautiful we are.
What if we always felt confident in our clothes.
And what if garments always brought out our best sides.

That is why we do not design for models on a catwalk, but for you.
It's time for fashion to empower you. And we intend to fight for that.

MORE CLARITY FOR THE CUSTOMER

2015–2016

- » During the year major changes took shape and results took a turn for the better.
- » The drivers were to develop KappAhl's customer offer, strengthen the gross margin and continued cost control.
- » Success factors have included gradual clarification of the collections as well as active work on price and campaign strategies.

DANNY FELTMANN

AGE 48

CURRENT

New President and Chief Executive Officer of KappAhl since 1 December 2015.

BACKGROUND

Sound experience of leading positions in fashion and retail trade, including H&M, Bang & Olufsen and Karmameju. Chairman of the board of Joe & the Juice and Beck Søndergaard.

YOU HAVE BEEN AT KAPPAHL FOR ALMOST A YEAR NOW. DESCRIBE YOUR FIRST YEAR AS CEO.

Fantastic! During the year I visited almost 50 stores, all the company's functions and several production offices in Asia. I was made extremely welcome everywhere and it was very exciting to get to know employees, as well as KappAhl's processes and company culture. It was inspiring, motivating and sometimes also challenging.

DURING THE YEAR YOU LAUNCHED KAPPAHL'S NEW BUSINESS PLAN "CLARITY FOR THE CUSTOMER". WHAT WAS YOUR IDEA BEHIND THE BUSINESS PLAN?

Our customer, a woman in the prime of life, plays a central role for us, since she makes many purchasing decisions and also buys for other family members from the men's and kid's departments. Our aim is to make KappAhl her first choice.

HOW WILL YOU DO IT?

It all starts with good collections that appeal to our customer. It is important to help her find her way and to give guidance and inspiration in the shopping experience. In some cases this may mean fewer articles but a clearer concept that helps the customer find the garments and accessories that feel right for her. For us, an inspiring shopping experience is not just about the individual garment, but also our communication, stores, sales material, packaging and presentation.

WHAT DID YOU FOCUS ON IN 2016?

We furthered the Woman concepts, to get them more coherent in terms of style, pattern and quality, thus making it even easier for customers to coordinate their garments. Through our new communication strategy, Feel, launched in autumn 2016, we also streamline our expression and

achieve even clearer and simpler communication. The communication strategy also contributes to the move from coupons and discounts to product and feelings. In combination this makes us clearer in our communication to our customer.

REGARDING PHYSICAL STORES, WHAT ARE THE EXPANSION PLANS FOR THE NEXT FEW YEARS?

The number of KappAhl stores will probably be the same in the next two to three years, but we are looking at all stores to ensure that they are optimised and that we are as effective as possible with the floor space we have. We continuously review concepts, reorganise, convert, open and close stores to ensure the highest possible sales per square metre.

WHAT IS THE OUTLOOK FOR CONCEPT STORES?

We opened more stand-alone concept stores during the year. At year-end we had a total of six stores; four Newbie Stores and two Hampton Republic 27 stores. Both concepts will now be reviewed.

YOU HAVE ALSO MADE SOME CHANGES IN YOUR ORGANISATION, TELL US ABOUT THEM!

To achieve our goals it is important for different functions to work in cooperation. So during the year we reorganised operations and introduced a matrix organisation. We have also conducted a great effort to train our leaders to strengthen the organisation.

Our company culture is characterised by our keywords; team spirit, creativity, clarity, energy and courage. Courage is particularly important for us just now. If you are making such a big move as we are, it is important to dare test new paths and do it seriously and with gusto! Curiosity is of course another important tool.

WHAT DO THE EMPLOYEES THINK OF THE BUSINESS PLAN?

I see great enthusiasm for our goals and the plan we have made for the next few years – and that makes me very proud. The employees’ commitment is also evident in this year’s employee study, in which all the question areas saw positive development. I am convinced that there is a tremendously strong connection between our employees’ faith in the organisation and the results we create. It is important to like your colleagues and the challenges you face at work, but also to feel that you are part of something bigger, and I think that feeling has grown during the year.

KAPPAHL HAS ALSO STRENGTHENED ITS SUSTAINABILITY ORGANISATION – HOW?

Yes, during the year we reviewed our sustainability organisation and strengthened it with new roles in design and range, as well as communication. All functions at KappAhl are responsible for driving the sustainability agenda in their part of the organisation and we want to strengthen understanding for sustainability throughout the company. For example, during the year we invested in sustainability training for our design and purchasing department and staff at the production offices. We believe it is important already at the design stage to ensure that the garments meet our requirements and are long-term sustainable.

WHAT IS THE GREATEST CHALLENGE FOR KAPPAHL IN THE AREA OF SUSTAINABILITY?

Making the journey towards an increased sustainable range profitable. There is movement towards increasingly sustainable fashion, both among consumers and producers, and we are glad that we are part of that journey. However, we know that customers mainly buy garments and accessories according to level of fashion and feeling, so it is important for us to communicate in the right way.

WHERE IS KAPPAHL HEADED NOW?

The idea behind Clarity for the Customer is that in a few years KappAhl will be a fashion chain with omnichannel presence. Already now, 80 per cent of our customers start their shopping trip digitally, regardless of whether they then make the purchase online or in store. Consequently, we want to refine our internal processes and ensure that we have a modern platform through investment in business systems. This is a condition for being able to create effective and profitable operations going forward.

WHEN YOU LOOK BACK ON YOUR FIRST YEAR AT KAPPAHL, WHAT ARE YOU MOST PROUD OF?

The result! During the year, by making a great joint effort, we reversed a negative trend. Together we succeeded in increasing sales and strengthening our operating margin. That is a good place to start from, as we take on the 2016/2017 financial year!

It all starts with good collections that appeal to our customer.

THIS IS KAPPAHL

At KappAhl **OUR PURPOSE** is to create a better everyday life for the woman in the prime of life, and her family, through offering a wide range of well-designed and feel good fashion, always in a sustainable way.

OUR BUSINESS

We achieve success by creating sustainable growth and profitability. This in turn allows us to invest and develop, as well as making our share attractive. We achieve our goals by:

- being a clear destination for our customers
- offering an attractive and well-coordinated range
- creating a well-performing sales and service organisation
- guiding our customers to modern and inspiring shopping experiences
- constantly developing our stores and Shop Online
- strengthening our brand to create loyal customers
- integrating sustainability in every part of our operations

OUR SUSTAINABILITY WORK

Sustainability is integrated into our daily work through our sustainability concept Future Friendly Fashion. This is based on:

- following global guidelines and principles, for example from the UN (including the ILO) and the OECD.
- applying the precautionary principle
- working proactively
- cooperating to achieve long-term sustainable development on cross-industry issues

Read more

about our business concept, our presence and our financial targets and sustainability targets on pages 44–49.

Our culture

TEAM SPIRIT We cooperate and treat each other professionally.

CREATIVITY We are open to new ideas and working methods.

CLARITY We focus on what is most important and aim for simplicity.

ENERGY We are committed, energetic and persistent.

COURAGE We dare to try out new things and take responsibility.

A CREATIVE WORKPLACE

Today we are one of the leading Nordic fashion chains with about 4,000 employees in nine countries. We work on anything from design and sales to marketing and distribution and together we sell hundreds of thousands of garments every day. Inspiring and guiding our customer to the right fashion for her is central for every employee at KappAhl.

WE AT KAPPAHL have different backgrounds, ages, knowledge and clothing styles. But we all have the same driving force: to provide many people with the opportunity of being well-dressed. Every day we get energy and inspiration from our customers. Our job is to give the same thing back.

We see enormous potential in all our committed employees, and we believe in them. Their decisions in everyday life mean that we achieve our targets, in the long and short term. We are open to what our employees think is challenging and want to change, and constantly work to refine our processes.

It is important for us to take responsibility for good working conditions at KappAhl and we work actively on issues such as gender equality, diversity and the work environment. The work is based on our policies and overall business strategies. Everyone who works at KappAhl is informed of our ethical guidelines and what they entail so as to form an approach to important issues such as corruption and conflicts of interest.

Actively working on the culture has resulted in a falling trend, from already low levels, in the number of employees who feel that they are discriminated in some way. (Read more in Part 2, page 49).

In Sweden, Finland and Norway all employees are covered by collective agreements, representing 87 per cent of KappAhl's employees. National legislation applies in other countries. In these countries in some cases we decide to augment the terms of employment beyond legislation.

POPULAR PLACE TO WORK

KappAhl is a popular place to work that offers varying challenges and opportunities for further development. There is a place here for people who want to develop, try working internationally and pursue a career. Our ambition is that seven out of ten management and specialist positions should be recruited internally.

OPPORTUNITY TO GROW

We want to give our employees opportunities to grow. The KappAhl Academy offers courses and training programmes to employees at all levels. All employees have been able to participate in skills development during the year; on average 11.6 training hours per employee. The customer meeting and sustainability issues permeate all our training programmes, so as to be able to meet our challenges, today and tomorrow.

CHALLENGES

- » Achieve increased effectiveness and profitability per employee hour worked.
- » Have the right skills in the right place in a changing industry.

OPPORTUNITIES

- » Continue to be a strong employer brand and attract the right competence.
- » Can offer good career opportunities and international experience.

THE YEAR'S IMPORTANT EVENTS

- » 47,000 training hours completed throughout the Group
- » Good results from the year's employee survey, our employees are proud of working at KappAhl
- » Major training initiative carried out in sales and service for all store staff
- » Seven out of ten managerial and specialist positions were recruited internally, in line with our objective

KEY RATIOS, EMPLOYEES

	2015/2016	2014/2015
Total number of employees	4,047	4,104
Full time positions (restated)	2,812	2,885
Percentage of women/men	91.5/9.5	92.6/7.4
Average age	37.3	35.8
Staff turnover (%)	14.0	10.5
Training hours per person	11.6	9.5
Sickness absence (%)	5.7	5.9

During the year, all employees in stores participated in sales and service training, focusing on the customer meeting, in the form of interactive eLearning and supervised training. This was highly appreciated by our staff and we have also received many encouraging comments from customers who feel they are receiving better service.

DEVELOPMENT OF MANAGERS TOO

For our employees in stores who aim to be store managers we offer training at the KappAhl Academy – Store Manager Trainees. The programme equips the participants for the challenges they will face as store managers, through both practical and theoretical training.

Those already working as managers at KappAhl can apply for our High Potential programme, a qualified programme in business methods and leadership in collaboration with the IHM Business School. The programme develops the leadership qualities of the participants and gives them tools to take more responsibility, extend their networks

and create strategic understanding for their role and KappAhl's entire operations.

Good managers need tools to be even better leaders. This year we continued our efforts to provide them with tools for coaching and feedback. We know that through engaging and clear communication we create the right conditions for our employees to continue to develop, while also receiving recognition for their important input.

EVEN THOSE NEW TO KAPPAHL SHOULD ENJOY THEIR WORK

When we recruit employees to KappAhl we seek people with drive and commitment. We have a popular process for making new employees feel welcome and able to take responsibility directly in their new roles. Our interactive introduction for new employees puts great weight on our values. Every employee has to complete it before their first working day. We want to give every new employee the best conditions for understanding and contributing to our customer's experience of KappAhl right from their first working day.

#LIFEATKAPPAHL

DO YOU WANT TO FIND OUT MORE ABOUT WORKING AT KAPPAHL?

On Instagram and Facebook our employees collect pictures from everyday life in stores and at the head office under the hashtag #lifeatkappahl

If you want to know more about what it's like to work at KappAhl, you can read assessments at www.careereye.se/arbetsgivare/kappahl (in Swedish)

GENDER EQUALITY AT THE TOP

WE HAVE A GENDER EQUAL MANAGEMENT TEAM and Board of Directors. This brought us recognition on AllBright's White List for 2016, which ranks Swedish listed companies from a gender equality perspective. Only 32 of the 282 companies listed on the Stockholm stock exchange qualified for the White List. We are proud to be one of them.

Read more at www.allbright.se/english/

WILL KAPPAHL BE THE YEAR'S EMPLOYER BRANDING COMPANY IN 2017?

KAPPAHL IS A STRONG employer brand and every year we attract a lot of talent. In autumn 2016 we were therefore nominated by Universum for the Year's Employer Branding company award for 2017. Keep your fingers crossed for us!

Do you want to work for us?

Our vacancies are listed at www.kappahl.com/positions.

An attractive workplace – VOICES FROM KAPPAHL'S EMPLOYEES

SATISFIED EMPLOYEES

WE THINK IT IS IMPORTANT that KappAhl's employees enjoy their work. When KappAhl's employees were given the opportunity to rate KappAhl as a workplace in the annual employee survey the score was high; 6.0 (5.7) out of 7. Development in all question areas is positive, for example the score for our sustainability work rose from 6.0 last year to 6.3 this year on the scale of seven.

The study also confirms our belief that our employees appreciate their workplace. On a scale of ten, half of all employees gave KappAhl a score of nine or ten in response to the question whether they would recommend KappAhl as a workplace to their friends and acquaintances.

We also see that our training initiative makes an impact – during the year we extended the number of training hours by 20 per cent – “KappAhl gives me good prospects for development” gets a score of 5.5 (5.3) out of 7.

Our employee survey, the KappAhl Attitude Survey, is conducted annually and the response rate is high; as many as 90 per cent of our employees participated in this year's survey. This shows great commitment to the workplace and that our employees feel part of our success.

It is a fun workplace with clear goals and high ambitions that rub off on me as an employee, which means you grow both in your professional role and as a person.

I get the chance to develop and am given challenges all the time. I feel I have great influence over how the work is to be organised and carried out in my store. My ideas are utilised and I am heard, seen and respected.

I am proud of working for a company with such a good attitude to its employees, the environment, quality and development.

OUR VALUE CHAIN

KappAhl's value chain is complex and contains many challenges, as well as opportunities. The work of integrating the sustainability aspect into all parts of the value chain— from design, to production, logistics, selling, marketing and consumption— is taking great steps forward every year. On the following pages you can read more about how we work to create profitable and sustainable operations throughout our value chain.

5. CONSUMPTION

At KappAhl we have a garment with us for a few days or weeks. The average customer uses garments for 2.2 years, according to WRAP*. It is important to give the garments a longer life than that and care for them in a way that reduces negative environmental impact. When the customer has finished using the garment, we take it, in whatever state, and send it on for reuse or recycling.
Read more on page 42.

4. SALES

Hundreds of thousands of people visit our stores and Shop Online every day. We work to inspire and guide customers to find their own style quickly and easily. We also work to create even more sustainable stores and to make KappAhl's values visible.
Read more on page 36.

I. DESIGN & PURCHASING

Our design and purchasing department creates about 6,000 articles every year. For us it is important to create attractive, value-for-money fashion for the woman in the prime of life and her family.

The garments should also meet our high standards of quality and sustainable design.

Read more on page 20.

2. PRODUCTION

KappAhl purchases production from 200 suppliers, the majority of them in Asia. We have production offices in China, Bangladesh, India, Turkey and Myanmar. Apart from good supplier relations, it is also important for us to ensure good working conditions and work for sustainable use of water, energy and chemicals, while maintaining high product quality.
Read more on page 26.

3. LOGISTICS

Every year about 50 million goods are moved from our suppliers to our distribution centre and then on to the stores' sales areas and home to the customers who buy via Shop Online. Timing is particularly important; so that the goods reach customers at the right time and that we use sustainable transport methods.
Read more on page 34.

*WRAP, Valuing our clothes – The true cost of how we design, use and dispose of clothing in the UK, 2012.

DESIGN AND PURCHASING

In our design and purchasing department we create value-for-money fashion that promotes our customer's style and reinforces her personality. We produce about 6,000 articles every year – always according to our customers' needs and focusing on sustainability.

DESIGN & PURCHASING

0.5% of KappAhl's total climate impact.

CHALLENGES

- » Creating an inspiring, attractive and clear range for our customer.
- » Hit the mark as regards trends, sizes, season and demand.
- » Limited access to sustainable solutions and materials.
- » Ensuring high quality at the right price.

MÖJLIGHETER

- » Our target group is growing, which is often overlooked by other fashion companies.
- » Increased demand for clear fashion concepts for the woman in the prime of life.
- » More customer demand for sustainable fashion.
- » Increased digitalisation, more people shopping online.
- » Sustainable decisions on design and purchasing bring improvements throughout the value chain.

UNDERSTANDING OUR CUSTOMER and being able to predict what she wants to wear in the coming season are central to our design and purchasing department. With her needs in mind we create the range we want her to find inspiring and attractive. During the year we developed our range model for women with a clearer offer, which has turned out well.

We constantly monitor trends and tendencies, silhouettes and details, to find inspiration for collections that feel just right for our customer. We want our design to make her feel good as she is and our collections to contribute to a shopping experience that is both inspiring and guiding.

Our customers think sustainability is important and studies show that more than 80 per cent of a product's impact on the environment is already determined at the design stage. The materials we use, how we construct our patterns and how we intend the garments to be used influence the garments' total environmental impact. Many sustainability initiatives in design and purchasing also contribute to reduced costs and more effective production.

Work on the range is partly controlled via range and sustainability strategies, product policy and the criteria for sustainable design that were drawn up during the year and are being implemented at the time of writing.

IMPORTANT EVENTS DURING THE YEAR

Increased focus on strategic range development with fewer but more well-coordinated fashion concepts. • *The KappAhl Sustainable Design Contest was held for the first time* • The proportion of sustainability labelled garments increased from 24 to 38 per cent • **Continued success for Newbie** • Concentration on Timeless Fashion – timeless design that lasts season after season

Designs value-for-money fashion with wide appeal!

SHARE OF NET SALES

■ Woman 52%
■ Kids 38%
■ Man 10%

OUR DESIGN PHILOSOPHY

AT KAPPAHL WE WANT TO HELP OUR CUSTOMERS to find and uplevel their unique style. The style will augment their personality and always create a good feeling. Our garments must have the right fashionability and the best fit. We work all the time to develop the hidden design in our garments. Clothes from KappAhl must be comfortable with the right details in the right place. Every week at our head office we try out new garments on real people who give their opinions on fit and feeling. No mannequin can do that!

WELL-COORDINATED FASHION CONCEPT

WE WORK STRATEGICALLY on range development. In the past year we continued to make our customer offer even clearer. By dividing our woman's department into four concepts we have created a clearer picture of our offer and streamlined our collections. The idea is to make it even easier for our customers to find their style and more simple-to-coordinate garments.

MARIA SEGERGREN,
KappAhl's new Vice President
Assortment & Design

Hi!

HOW DOES KAPPAHL CREATE AN ATTRACTIVE RANGE?

"We focus on our customer! We know she wants exciting and interesting collections that feel modern and we endeavour to provide them. Our range must always be clear and well-coordinated. We respect our customer and her wish to be well-dressed and focus on producing garments and accessories with the right fashionability that make her feel good as she is.

HOW DO YOU WORK STRATEGICALLY ON RANGE DEVELOPMENT?

"With all the knowledge we have about our customer we can produce collections with a clear idea that is sustained all the way from drawing board to customer's wardrobe. We make sure we capture trends that are right for our customer and that they are in the stores at the right time. We are also making great steps in the area of sustainability and now integrate sustainability criteria into our design process.

WHAT HAS KAPPAHL ACHIEVED DURING THE YEAR IN RANGE DEVELOPMENT?

"We see that our concentration on clarity, from concept to store, is paying off. One example is our Always Black collection of black trousers, which is very successful.

WHAT ATTRACTED YOU TO START WORKING AT KAPPAHL?

"There is so much potential! And I am enormously impressed by the sustainability work. It is quite fantastic and something we really should give ourselves more credit for.

STRÖMBERG

With a fondness for Italian elegance and well-dressed classics, the Strömberg collection offers men's fashion with confidence in its seams. Strömberg is designed by the KappAhl's design team in partnership with Glenn Strömberg. He is involved both in producing the collection and being a model in the campaigns.

ALWAYS BLACK

Our black trousers in the Always Black collection are in six models with a fit that is always in place. Both the black colour and the style have staying power. But most important of all: they feel good to wear, regardless of the occasion. The collection is very popular with our customers and is a real sales success.

KAPPAHL SUSTAINABLE DESIGN CONTEST

WE WANT TO ENCOURAGE TOMORROW'S FASHION CREATORS to design sustainable fashion. So this year we launched the KappAhl Sustainable Design Contest for fashion students who want to be part of developing future sustainable design solutions.

Lovisa Sandrine Malmberg Gomis, who studied at the ESMOD fashion school in Paris, was declared this year's winner. Her entry is based on the idea of designing intelligent garments that can have different areas of use and thus a longer life. A blouse that can be transformed into a party dress, for example. The entry is based on zero waste, a principle in which left-over fabric is minimised in manufacture, which is entirely in line with the spirit of the contest. The winning garments will be launched in KappAhl stores in spring 2017.

THE KAPPAHL SUSTAINABLE DESIGN CONTEST PANEL OF JUDGES

Emilia de Poret, fashion journalist • Dr Kate Goldsworthy, Textiles Environment Design (TED) in London • Paul Laing, head of design, KappAhl • Karin Verdoes, designer, KappAhl • Eva Kindgren de Boer, Sustainability Coordination Manager Production, KappAhl

RÜKIE FASHION FOR TWEENIES

TWEENIES, CHILDREN BETWEEN 8 AND 12 YEARS, are increasingly inspired by the clothing styles of older teenagers and bloggers and what kid's departments offer perhaps doesn't always feel right for this target group. So we developed Rükie, our answer to a tweeny's wish for decent clothes. It is important for us that the clothes are cool, but also that the garments convey a feeling of warmth and pep. To reach out to our tweenies we have marketed the concept on social media such as Kik and Snapchat.

The fashion lab

ALL THE CLOTHES SOLD in KappAhl's stores are designed in the design studio at the head office in Möln-dal. Many different experiences, skills and occupational roles are needed to be completely successful in design and purchasing. Among our employees are designers, design assistants, controllers, buyers, buyer's assistants, pattern constructors, design and purchasing managers and collection managers. During the year we have also augmented our purchasing organisation with a sustainability coordinator.

Inspiration for new collections comes from every quarter: partly from our own customer surveys and assortment council with store representatives, partly from travel and fashion weeks, trend websites, magazines and trend spotting of anything from architecture to gardens.

The major trends are picked up by KappAhl's designers far in advance, but in parallel we also need to work

at a faster pace and with shorter decision lines when new trends turn up and must be quickly added to the assortment. In that case suppliers in Turkey, for example, are engaged with shorter delivery times.

Normally work is in progress on up to three seasons at a time and garments and collections are sketched and deliberated over that only turn up in the stores about 9–12 months later.

The pattern constructors play an important part in reinterpreting the designers' ideas and sketches into patterns and instructions. They create patterns, make measurement lists, change samples and participate in fittings. All to create the best possible fit.

The purchasers decide what is to be manufactured, how much and when. They also set the prices and negotiate with our suppliers in collaboration with our own offices in the production countries.

SIZES THAT MEASURE UP

DO YOU BUY CLOTHES in size 38 in Sweden? Size 12 in the UK and 44 in Italy? Sizes vary depending on which EU country you shop in. In addition, they can vary from one fashion chain to another in the same country. Strange? Yes! Now it's time to rectify the problem.

A European project to harmonise sizes in the EU has been running since 1994. Lotta Silow, whose ordinary job is a pattern constructor at KappAhl, represents Sweden in the European standardisation group.

This year the group has agreed on a proposal for a new size standard for womenswear, menswear and kidswear. The proposal is based on bust measurements for the upper body and hip measurements for the lower body. The measurements are in centimetres and now the sizes will reflect the measurements. Trousers that are now marked as size 38 will be marked 96 and fit people with a hip measurement of 94–98 cm. If necessary the primary measurement can be supplemented by a secondary measurement, such as height.

The proposal is expected to be approved in spring 2017 and will be implemented in EU countries in the next few years. The work on a common European size standard is entirely in line with KappAhl's ambition to achieve more clarity for customers and a good fit. The new size system will also make it easier to buy clothes online. If you know your measurements you know which size to order!

TRAINING FOR SUSTAINABLE DESIGN

WE STRIVE for all our products to meet our sustainable design requirements. The journey there will offer challenges and to be better equipped in 2016 our entire design and purchasing department is undergoing training in sustainable design.

Within the framework of the training we ensure that all our designers, buyers and production office staff have a good knowledge of sustainability challenges, for example in choice of material, use of chemicals and working conditions. Good for the environment, good for all of us!

38%

SUSTAINABILITY LABELLED FASHION

EVERY YEAR THE PERCENTAGE OF SUSTAINABILITY LABELLED FASHION will increase at KappAhl. This year we have used about 15,300 tonnes of raw materials for our range, 73 per cent of which consists of material from renewable sources and <0.5 per cent consists of recycled synthetic fibre. Sustainability labelled products at KappAhl are manufactured from more sustainable material or are certified under Oeko-Tex. During the year we increased our share of sustainability labelled fashion from 24 to 38 per cent.

CONTINUED SUCCESS FOR NEWBIE

NEWBIE IS ONE OF OUR most successful concepts and its fan club is growing every day. The concept of kid's and baby clothes is characterised by a value-for-money range that will stand up to being used and passed on for generations. The sustainability approach has permeated Newbie right from the start in 2010 and its cotton has always been organic. From this year, all garments are manufactured from sustainable material and many of them are certified under GOTS (Global Organic Textile Standards), showing that the garments are made from organically grown cotton with strict rules for the use of chemicals and high social requirements.

PRODUCTION

Our production during the year was with 203 (200) suppliers, mainly in Asia but also in Europe. We impose high requirements on our suppliers and often work in industry initiatives to contribute in the best way to sustainable development in the environment and working conditions in the countries of production.

90 PER CENT of our purchases are made from our suppliers in Asia. Our sustainability strategy is the starting point in dealing with the major sustainability challenges in production. This includes human rights and corruption, working conditions and wages, sustainable materials, creating cleaner production and achieving reduced use of water, energy and chemicals. We see great opportunities to contribute in various ways and reach out to the approximately 124,000 employees at our suppliers

and even more who work earlier in the value chain. Our binding Code of Conduct is an important policy instrument in our work, together with our ethical guidelines and strategies and production guidelines. We have production offices in Bangladesh, India, China, Turkey and Myanmar, which deal with the day-to-day contacts with our suppliers. We locate our production with the supplier that can best meet our requirements regarding price, quality, sustainability and reliability of delivery.

PRODUCTION

61.4% of KappAhl's total climate impact.

CHALLENGES

- » Good suppliers in terms of quality, price and sustainability, for example working conditions and fair wages at all stages of production.
- » Cleaner production, in terms of water, energy and chemicals.
- » Access to sustainably cultivated raw materials, such as sustainably cultivated cotton.
- » Exchange rate effects on purchase prices.

OPPORTUNITIES

- » Enhanced partnerships with suppliers, for higher quality and productivity.
- » Contribute to sustainable development, for example in environmental and working conditions in the production chain.
- » Utilise the flexibility of not having our own factories.

IMPORTANT EVENTS DURING THE YEAR

Joined Canopy for more sustainable cellulose fibres • Joined the Ethical Trading Initiative, ETI • Joined the Organic Cotton Accelerator, OCA • The fashion industry initiative SWAR, where KappAhl is one of the initiators, won the sustainability award of the year at the Habit Fashion Gala • More than half of our cotton comes from more sustainable farms • Establishment in Myanmar is continuing

MYANMAR – FUTURE MARKET

DURING THE YEAR KAPPAHL opened a production office in Myanmar as well as placing the first test orders. KappAhl sees Myanmar as a future market, but the country also has many challenges in the area of sustainability and we are therefore keeping strictly to our principles when selecting new suppliers. KappAhl is a member of the Business for Social Responsibility (BSR) and participates in the BSR Myanmar Responsible Sourcing Working Group.

10 LARGE SUPPLIERS

IN 2015/2016 THE 10 LARGEST suppliers accounted for 30 (30) per cent of our purchases. 90 per cent of our goods are manufactured in Asia. Coordinated production means increased quality, better control and greater opportunities for influence.

SAFE PRODUCTS WITHOUT DANGEROUS CHEMICALS

THE ISSUE OF CHEMICALS IS CENTRAL in our operations and is a matter that affects both the environment and the people along the entire value chain, from farmer to customer. Our *Test and Manufacturing Guide* is our most important policy instrument as regards the use of chemicals in production. The work is governed by REACH, the EU Regulation on Chemicals, and our membership of the Swedish Nordic Chemicals Group. We are working to phase out more and more chemicals, such as phthalates, used as softening agents.

To ensure that the products meet our high requirements our quality engineers at the head office work closely with our production offices. Our work is based on our own process, No Risk. It means that during the year

we have carried out almost a thousand random sample checks on finished goods in independent authorised laboratories. Tests are carried out at all suppliers. Children's clothes have priority, and the garments we wear next to the skin, such as underwear, t-shirts and vests.

In 2015/2016 we carried out 932 random sample checks and 98 per cent of the garments passed. The garments that did not pass were mainly from new suppliers whom we train to ensure that they phase out the chemicals we do not approve. After that we carry out new tests to ensure that the chemicals are no longer used. KappAhl has not recalled any products during the year due to chemicals.

You can find more information on our chemicals restrictions at www.kappahl.com/sustainability

The Code

OUR CODE OF CONDUCT

KAPPAHL WANTS TO CONTRIBUTE TO LONG-TERM sustainable development in the countries and factories we buy goods from. Together with the Code of Conduct for suppliers, our sustainability strategy governs how we collaborate with suppliers and their factories in these areas.

The Code of Conduct, which all suppliers undertake to follow, covers important areas such as forced labour, child labour, the freedom of association and organisation, wages and working hours, safety at the workplace, as well as environmental aspects such as correct water purification.

Our Code of Conduct is available to read at www.kappahl.com/sustainability

MONITORING THE CODE

KAPPAHL CONDUCTS A CONTINUOUS DIALOGUE about the Code of Conduct with our suppliers and our employees at our local production offices annually carry out hundreds of inspections and follow-up visits to our suppliers.

We have our own employees who monitor the Code of Conduct in three steps: identify deviations for the Code of Conduct, initiate improvement measures, supervise and support the work of improvement through transparent dialogue. Another important task is cooperation and coordination with colleagues in the purchasing organisation to ensure that production is at factories that live up to our requirements.

When we identify deviations with our requirements our objective is to contribute to change instead of ending the partnership. The supplier and factory must draw up an action plan that describes how the deviations are to be corrected systematically and sustainably, when the actions are to be completed and who is responsible for ensuring this is done. "Measures for improvement usually benefit all parties – the worker gets a better work situation, the supplier a better factory where employees are satisfied and KappAhl gets a more sustainable supplier chain," explains Magnus Mattsson, Global Social Compliance Manager at KappAhl.

The most common deviations are in the area of wages and working hours. We also see challenges in fire safety and conditions of employment, for example. If a supplier does not cooperate, a factory does not live up to the basic requirements or does not carry out promised improvements, we limit or stop the placing of orders. Read more in Part 2, pages 49.

INSPECTIONS AND FOLLOW-UP VISITS

IN 2015/2016 WE MADE 298 (418) inspections and follow-up visits at the suppliers' factories. The decrease is partly due to our having fewer new suppliers this year and that we have reduced the number of factories in China.

We rank factories according to how well they live up to our requirements: Unsatisfactory, Temporarily Approved and Approved. Unsatisfactory means that the factory does not meet the basic requirements and can therefore not be used for production for KappAhl. The first time we inspect a factory, if it meets our basic requirements it is always ranked as Temporarily Approved, as more than one visit is necessary to verify how well a factory lives up to our requirements. Within twelve months the factory must be inspected again and then meet the requirements for Approved. While we are in partnership with a supplier and factory we continue to visit the factory regularly and work for further improvements. During the year 100 per cent of the new factories associated with a production office (55 new factories) were inspected. The factories inspected in the category of agents and importers are in risk countries or have reached a certain order value. 16 per cent of the new factories (38 new factories) in the category of agents and importers were inspected.

All inspections carried out during the year on new and old factories in risk countries in the category of agents and importers correspond to 78 per cent of the order value in this category. Inspections at new factories carried out during the year correspond altogether to 92 per cent of our order value. For more information on action taken in relation to suppliers during the year, please see Part 2, page 49.

	2015/2016	2014/2015
Number of inspections	176	190
Number of follow-up visits	122	228
Number of factories	349	354
Approved, %	47	53
Temporarily approved, %	37	33
Unsatisfactory, %	1	1
Not inspected*, %	15	13

* Constitutes factories in the category of agents and importers that have not reached a certain order value or are not in a risk country.

"I regard my land as sustainable agricultural land and not as a manufacturing unit. No one can imagine a world without agriculture."

Kashibai, female cotton farmer in Maharashtra, India, who is participating in the project for female cotton farmers

MORE SUSTAINABLE COTTON WITH THE BCI

MORE THAN HALF of all cotton in our garments is now more sustainably cultivated and our objective is that this will apply to all cotton by 2020. An important step in this direction is membership of the Better Cotton Initiative (BCI). The BCI trains cotton farmers in cultivation of cotton with less water and chemicals, which is positive for the environment and the health of the workers. The BCI has many other advantages. Not least as regards conditions for the farmers, workers and their families. The money saved by the farmer by using less water, chemicals and fertilizers goes for example to higher wages for employees and schooling for the children. In the 2015/2016 financial year KappAhl trained 1,100 (1,950) farmers in accordance with the BCI's guidelines. In the production of raw materials KappAhl has limited opportunities to promote better working conditions. Our strategy there is to be active through cooperation initiatives such as the BCI, which reaches all the way to the cotton producers.

TRAINING FOR FEMALE COTTON FARMERS

WITHIN THE FRAMEWORK OF OUR membership of the better cotton initiative (BCI) we run projects to train farmers in sustainable cotton cultivation. During the 2015/2016 financial year we initiated a project together with the independent organisation Cotton Connect and four industry colleagues to support female cotton farmers in India. The 1,546 women participating in the project are given access to training that gives them knowledge of crop rotation, how to protect their harvest, reduce their water consumption and the advantages of bio-fertiliser that adds long-acting and easily accessible plant nutrients to the soil.

Canopy

– FOR SUSTAINABLE CELLULOSE FIBRES

ABOUT 10 PER CENT of our garments contain cellulose-based fibres such as viscose, lyocell and modal. As studies show that a third of the world's viscose comes from endangered primeval forests, during the year KappAhl joined Canopy, an organisation that works to ensure that the textile industry's cellulose-based fibres come from sustainable forestry. Our objective is that all cellulose fibres purchased must come from Canopy-approved suppliers. The work is expected to be fully implemented in 2017. Consequently we are conducting training and inspections at our suppliers and helping them to meet Canopy's requirements.

ORGANIC COTTON ACCELERATION, OCA

IT TAKES THREE YEARS for a cotton farmer to redirect production from conventional to organic cultivation. It is a long and demanding journey. To create incentives for more farmers to take this step, during the year we joined the Organic Cotton Accelerator, which supports farmers who redirect their production.

WINNING PARTNERSHIPS FOR CLEANER WATER

Textile production is highly water-intensive and in many Asian countries the textile industry is the fourth largest user of water. According to the World Bank the textile industry also causes 20 per cent of global water pollution. We take the water issue seriously and are therefore involved in industry initiatives to help find solutions and spread knowledge of the issue in our production countries.

PACT IN BANGLADESH

We are members of the Partnership for Cleaner Textile, PaCT, in Bangladesh. Through the membership we ensure that our producers use less water, energy and chemicals. This means that we have a positive influence on local communities where our goods are produced. PaCT estimates that water consumption at the participating factories has decreased by 14.4 million cubic metres and emissions of greenhouse gases have decreased by 188,000 tonnes on an annual basis.

WINNING INDUSTRY INITIATIVE IN INDIA

In 2013 KappAhl, together with the Swedish International Development Agency (Sida), the Stockholm International Water Institute (SIWI) and two industry colleagues, started the successful Sustainable Water Resources (SWAR) project for cleaner textile production in India. As part of the project we have worked with 14 of our suppliers to improve the processes and increase knowledge of the water issue. In autumn 2015 SWAR was awarded the Sustainability Award of the Year at the Habit Fashion Gala.

SWAR has now expanded and today some twenty Swedish companies are involved in the Sweden Textile Water Initiative (STWI), which also includes factories in China, Bangladesh and Turkey. The factories, suppliers and subcontractors that participated in the project have saved more than 360 million litres of water, 7 per cent of their water requirements, annually in recent years. This corresponds to the water requirements of more than 3.5 million people. They have also saved 402 tonnes of chemicals per year. 83 per cent of the value of our purchased goods in Bangladesh and India is covered by PaCT or STWI.

ZERO TOLERANCE OF CHILD LABOUR

KAPPAHL HAS ZERO TOLERANCE of child labour. Our code of conduct defines child labour in accordance with ILO Convention No. 138. We encourage our suppliers to draw up and apply policies and procedures to ensure that children are not employed in their own operations or by subcontractors and state how important it is to check the age of job applicants. We have a clear plan for how we are to act if child labour is encountered. It means we act for the best possible solution until the legal working age is reached. This year we identified one case, in China. A fifteen-year-old boy was working in his summer holiday. As this was a summer job, our action was limited to ensuring that he was paid wages for the time he worked.

THE HUNGER PROJECT

APART FROM THE WORK at the factories, KappAhl contributes actively to local development in the countries where we buy raw materials and production. We support the Hunger project, a global organisation that with women in focus trains and strengthens people's opportunities to drive their own development.

Read more at www.thp.org

NEW OPPORTUNITIES FOR POOR WOMEN IN DHAKA

WE WANT TO HELP increase women's opportunities and position in society in our production countries. We do this for example by offering training, which paves the way to earning a living and a more independent life for women and their children. In 2010 we started our training centre for vulnerable women in the outskirts of Dhaka. Here we receive women between the ages of 18 and 35, who come from really poor circumstances and lack formal education. Seeing them grow day by day is a powerful experience. Half of the population of Bangladesh lack basic reading and arithmetic skills. Therefore the participants learn to write their own name and

count to a hundred at the beginning of the training. Women's rights, health and safety are other subjects that are taught alongside sewing and dressmaking. Each participant receives a financial contribution during their period of study and they are offered medical care and medicine where necessary. All the women are offered work after the training and there are examples of previous students now having achieved positions of responsibility. This year 94 women received training and since the start in 2010 almost 500 women have completed the three-month training. We think all women should be allowed to control their own lives.

DO YOU WANT TO KNOW MORE?

Our partner, TCM, has produced a film on the work at the training centre. www.youtube.com/watch?v=YMCipOJ6DRw

*Now I work in a factory.
I feel good and can look
after my family well.*

SHILPI, former student at our training centre in Dhaka

VISITING BANGLADESH

IT IS IMPORTANT FOR US to spread knowledge of our production and our production countries to our employees. In autumn 2015 a group of Swedish KappAhl employees visited Bangladesh together with three representatives of the Swedish Commercial Employees' Union, two of whom also work in KappAhl stores and are employee representatives on KappAhl's

Board of Directors. On the trip they were given training in sustainability at our production offices and visited a factory that produces our goods, as well as our training centre for poor women in Dhaka. After the trip they described their experiences and KappAhl's sustainability work in Bangladesh to their colleagues at several seminars.

ETHICAL TRADING INITIATIVE, ETI

FAIR WAGES and overtime are important issues for KappAhl and at the same time are among the most complex issues in our production countries in Asia. We consider that KappAhl best contributes to positive progress on these issues through cooperating with other companies and organisations. After actively seeking partnerships on the issue, in April 2016 we joined the Ethical Trading Initiative, which brings together companies, trade unions and interest organisations that all want to develop working conditions for factory workers globally.

THE ACCORD

– FOR BETTER SAFETY IN BANGLADESH

SAFETY ISSUES have long been a neglected area in Bangladesh, where factory buildings are often built vertically and a fire can have disastrous consequences. As a direct effect of the disaster in the Rana Plaza factory outside Dhaka, with more than 1,100 dead and 2,500 injured, in April 2013 “The Accord on Fire and Building Safety in Bangladesh”, was started, a project to guarantee a more secure and safe working environment for millions of textile workers in the country. KappAhl has been a member since 2013 and cooperates in the project with more than 200 international industry colleagues, international labour organisations and local trade unions. Since the Accord was established, more than 1,500 factories have been inspected, and now follow-up visits are being conducted to check the improvements made. We see clear improvements regarding fire and building safety in the factories we work with. More information can be found at www.bangladeshaccord.org

LIST OF FACTORIES

ON KAPPAHL'S WEBSITE you will find a list of the factories that our suppliers use to produce our clothes. We have published this since autumn 2013 at www.kappahl.com/sustainability

LOGISTICS

Every year we transport about 50 million goods to our stores and home to customers who buy via Shop Online. We aim for both environmentally and cost effective logistics throughout our value chain.

LOGISTICS

4.5% of KappAhl's total climate impact.

CHALLENGES

- » Timing and effectiveness, so that the right product is at the right store at the right time and at the right price.
- » Climate problems lead to a greater need for environmentally effective transportation.
- » Deficient working conditions in parts of the transport sector.

OPPORTUNITIES

- » Increased utilisation of coordination advantages following from KappAhl's size.
- » Further develop KappAhl's existing environmental and cost effective distribution solutions.
- » Further integration of eCommerce and store logistics.

STORAGE SPACE IN OUR STORES IS LIMITED, since areas must preferably be used for selling. That is why the timing of distribution is important. The goods should be out on the store floor among salespeople and customers, in the right store at the right time. In that way we can increase sales and

reduce the need for price reductions. Working to increase efficiency in logistics is also in line with our sustainability work, as it leads to reduced emissions per garment. KappAhl coordinates logistics and has a common distribution centre for the entire group.

IMPORTANT EVENTS DURING THE YEAR

- Continued optimisation of the supply chain from production to store • 80 per cent of all sea transport is with shipping companies that are verified according to the Clean Shipping Index
- Further improved filling ratio in the entire chain from factory to store

CLEAN SHIPPING NETWORK

SINCE 2008 WE BELONG TO THE Clean Shipping Network, an organisation that promotes more sustainable maritime transport. Carrying goods by sea gives less emissions than using air or road transport. But sea transport nevertheless has sustainability challenges, such as emissions, waste management and working conditions on the ships. The Clean Shipping Network provides a tool – the Clean Shipping Index – that lists the shipping companies that work to improve conditions and reduce the environmental impact of their sea transport. In the 2015/2016 financial year, 80 per cent of the shipping companies we use were verified by the Clean Shipping Index. We have also participated in a call for more shipping companies to take responsibility for their ships when they are scrapped, since ship-breaking is a great problem in Asia today.

HIGH REQUIREMENTS ON SUSTAINABILITY

WE WORK ACTIVELY to reduce our environmental impact from transport, for example by using sea transport as the first alternative for transporting goods from production countries to our distribution centre. To reduce costs and environmental impact for each item of freight, we endeavour to use group shipment and smart packing for the highest filling ratio. We also impose environmental requirements on all carriers, regardless of mode of transport.

DISTRIBUTION OF MODES OF TRANSPORT

from production country to store, based on the number of tonne-kilometres*

*There is no historical data, since in previous years we have reported distribution of modes of transport from production country to distribution centre.

IMPROVED FILLING RATIO

WE ENDEAVOUR TO pack our goods as effectively as possible. During the 2015/2016 financial year we reduced our transport capacity needs from the distribution centre to stores by almost seven per cent by packing the goods more efficiently. This results in both reduced environmental impact and reduced cost per transported item.

RIGHT ITEM IN THE RIGHT PLACE

TO INCREASE SALES per square metre and speed of sales we are refining our allocation strategy. Deliveries of goods to stores will in future be steered by the store's unique needs and sales to ensure that the right item is in the right place. We have also augmented our organisation with a merchandiser for each market, who analyses and optimises our sales at both country and store level.

BETTER SUPPLY CHAIN FOR INCREASED SALES

IN RECENT YEARS we have changed our supply chain by fine-tuning the process all the way from packing in the production countries to store inventories. Our objective is to reduce store inventories and give our store staff even more time for meeting customers. Ultimately the improvements are to lead to increased sales and gross profit.

As part of this, during the year we continued to improve the supply chain to stores. By making our processes more effective we have further reduced our lead times. This speeds up the supply of garments, and helps reduce store inventories.

SUCCESS FOR SHOP ONLINE

ECOMMERCE IS STEADILY GROWING and we see that customers increasingly seek more inspiration in social media and that they like to click to order products online, often from smartphones. They can do that when they have time, regardless of whether it is on the bus, on the way home from work or in the evening when the children are in bed.

Even among customers who prefer to shop in a store we see that many have started their shopping trip digitally – via social media, the customer club app or Shop Online. Our digital presence is therefore becoming more and more important when creating KappAhl's image.

KappAhl's eCommerce has progressed very well in terms of turnover since the start in 2011. Sales have been further augmented through the technological development that has taken place since then. During

the year we started to show garments in Shop Online on models that are popular with our customers and this has contributed to the positive trend.

We follow closely how customers' consumption patterns develop so as to provide shopping that is simple, guiding and inspiring. Searches in Shop Online give us a pointer as to what customers want from us. This is valuable information for our designers and buyers!

We also continue to create an inspiring shopping experience. Our customers must be able to shop where, how and when they like and always meet the same KappAhl. In 2016/17 we will introduce what is called Click & Collect. Our customers will then be able to collect the goods they have ordered online in our stores. We will guide towards the best shopping experience, regardless of channel.

SALES

Every day we meet hundreds of thousands of customers, in stores and in our Shop Online. We inspire and guide them to find their own style, all to give them the best service.

EVERYTHING STARTS AND ENDS with the customer meeting. It is for our customer that we create our collections and we inspire and help her to find fashion that feels right. It is also in the meeting with the customer that we gain valuable information for creating attractive collections and offers in future.

KappAhl should always be accessible and offer good service, regardless of whether the customer meets us in a store or Shop Online to make a purchase, wherever she is or whenever she has time. Shop Online also offers the customer who prefers to shop in a store the opportunity for inspiration and research before she visits us in store.

We work purposefully to optimise sales per square metre and increase sales speed by ensuring that the right item is in the right place at the right time. During the year we also launched our new price strategy, focusing on full price sales and a changed campaign strategy, which was very successful.

In November 2015 we launched our Shop Online in Poland and now we have Shop Online on all our markets. We are working now to further strengthen KappAhl going forward with inspiring and personal shopping experiences, regardless of whether we meet our customer in store or online.

IMPORTANT EVENTS DURING THE YEAR

The store concept For You was rolled out in another 19 stores • Two new Newbie Stores were opened in Sweden and one in Norway • The popular Hampton Republic 27 concept has its first two own stores in Sweden • All store employees have completed sales and service training, with a focus on the customer meeting • Shop Online was launched in Poland • Launch of digital customer club in Sweden and Finland • National partner in the Eurovision Song Contest

INCREASED SALES

SALES INCREASED BY 3.0 per cent compared with the previous year, partly due to gradual clarifications of the collections and changed and active work on price and campaign strategies.

SALES IN OUR MARKETS, SEK MILLION

LIFE & STYLE BY KAPPAHL

WHEN KAPPAHL STARTED THE FASHION CLUB Life&Style by KappAhl in 2011 it was the first step in a long-term strategy of strengthening the customer relation. The club is very successful and today has a membership of several million customers.

In our unique customer club app we gather inspiration, offers and customer bonus to make it easier for our members. The app was launched in Norway in autumn 2014 and was very popular from the start. In autumn 2016 we also successfully launched the app for our members in Sweden and Finland. Today the app has more than 250,000 active users.

SALES
10.2% of KappAhl's
total climate impact.

CHALLENGES

- » Increase sales in comparable stores and the number of goods per customer.
- » More effective delivery procedures that give more time for serving customers.
- » Inspire and help customers to easily find the right look in the channel of their choice.
- » Reduce energy consumption and waste.

OPPORTUNITIES

- » KappAhl is a sought-after tenant in store properties.
- » Augment the customer experience via stores in combination with Shop Online.
- » Clearer presentation of goods and more focus on in-store service, for increased sales.

SHOP ONLINE NOW IN POLAND

After launching Shop Online in Poland in November 2015 KappAhl is now accessible round the clock, every day, in all our sales markets.

FOR YOU A STORE CONCEPT FOR YOU

OUR STORES should feel welcoming and well-thought-out. The store concept is intended to strengthen the customer experience through modern and attractive design where the range, its structure and priorities stand out and are displayed in the best way. For You is a clear store concept to attract, inspire and engage our customers to shop and stay loyal.

The For You store concept was launched in 2014. In the 2015/2016 financial year it was rolled out in 19 stores and is now in a total of 49 stores. In autumn 2016 For You 2.0 was launched, a refinement and development of the concept aimed at being more streamlined and clear.

Our customers like For You. We see good results in the stores that have been converted. Customers stay longer and the average purchase is clearly higher.

KAPPAHL EUROVISION

AT KAPPAHL WE LOVE Eurovision and so we are proud to have been a national partner to the 2016 Eurovision Song Contest.

The contest took place in Stockholm in May 2016 and for the entire festival week there were long winding queues to our tent in the Eurovillage – the popular festival area in Kungsträdgården in Stockholm. There our visitors had the opportunity to dress up in glummy Eurovision outfits and record music videos. The festive mood could also be felt in our stores, where we held competitions to win Eurovision tickets and showed our *Let's Celebrate* campaign.

A MORE SUSTAINABLE STORE CONCEPT

WE CONTINUALLY DEVELOP our store concept For You regarding sustainability. For example by imposing requirements on choice of material, reuse and responsible production. When purchasing store material we now require that at least 30 per cent be made of recycled material. All wood must be FSC labelled and substances such as lead and nickel are not allowed. Since spring 2016 all stores that are converted are supplied with LED lighting that reduce electricity consumption considerably compared with the previous metal halide lighting. Our bags are made entirely from recycled plastic or FSC labelled paper.

ONWARDS FOR **MAN**

DURING THE YEAR WE STREAMLINED CUSTOMER FLOW. The structure and placing of departments, fitting rooms and cash points have been updated. The men's department has been moved forward, the women's department has been given a clearer, coherent area and the kid's department has been placed furthest in, as it functions well as a destination. This is a classic customer flow that supports our offering an assortment for the entire family. The updated goods display and more visible men's department have helped to increase its sales.

Sound ideals

EVER SINCE KAPPAHL WAS established more than 60 years ago we have embraced the fundamental value that all people are fine just as they are. We stand for inclusive, sound ideals, which actively permeate both our range and our communication.

Through our wide range of garments in different sizes and fits we show that fashion is not limited by size.

In our campaigns and tonality we endeavour to uplevel our customers' self-esteem and well-being. Our customer should have a good feeling. That is why for example we think diversity when choosing models and we have mannequins with healthy shapes and we do not sell garments that may be perceived as offensive. We also consider our marketing carefully before launch.

Our approach has meant historically that we have had few complaints against our marketing, which is otherwise relatively common in the fashion industry. For example, there were no complaints to the Swedish Advertising Ombudsman in the 2015/2016 financial year.

TWELVE NEW STORES

AN IMPORTANT PART OF OUR PLAN. A step in that direction is to open stand-alone stores. Our Newbie Store concept has been successful right from the start. In the 2015/2016 financial year we opened three Newbie Stores and now have four stores. In autumn 2016 another three stores will open. The popular Hampton Republic 27 collection also opened its first two dedicated stores in Sweden during the year. We plan to open five to ten stores for each concept before we evaluate any continued establishment.

During the year we also opened seven new KappAhl stores, and converted our flagship store on Drottninggatan in Stockholm. We closed 13 KappAhl stores, most of them in Poland, where we are working to strengthen profitability.

newbie

FINE AS I AM

CHILD OR ADULT, WE WANT EVERYONE TO FEEL THAT THEY ARE FINE JUST AS THEY ARE. For the third year in a row we therefore invited children to take part in a design competition on the theme "Fine as I am". The winning entry was printed on cloth bags that were sold in KappAhl stores and some of the proceeds went to the child rights organisations Bris (Children's Rights in Society) in Sweden, Kors på halsen (Cross your Heart) in Norway, the Mannerheim League in Finland and the Nobody's Children Foundation in Poland (FDN). The year's Christmas campaign for "Fine as I am" was also popular with customers and gave good contributions to the organisations. In spring 2016 KappAhl was declared the Bris Partner of the Year. "We are happy, proud and very pleased!" says Charlotte Högberg, head of sponsoring at KappAhl.

Feel – OUR NEW COMMUNICATION CONCEPT

FASHION SHOULD GIVE STRENGTH AND STYLE as well as being accessible regardless of size or shape. We see it is time to change the way we regard fashion today and create fashion that makes our customers feel good in themselves. With our new communication concept Feel, KappAhl presents garments designed with the real woman in focus, aimed at bringing out the best in each individual woman. In autumn 2016 the campaign is fronted by Paulina Porizkova.

GREEN ELECTRICITY IN STORES

We want to reduce our environmental impact, so during the year we signed an agreement on renewable electricity for our stores in the Nordic countries. 66 per cent of all energy we purchased in 2015/2016 is renewable. The search for the right supplier in Poland to achieve the target of 100% renewable energy is in progress.

SUSTAINABLE TO THE SMALLEST DETAIL

KAPPAHL AIMS to use more sustainable material, even in such small details as labels. Our paper labels are mainly manufactured from FSC labelled or recycled paper and cut with straight corners to reduce left-over paper. From this year we also use recycled polyester in all our washing instruction labels, apart from for Newbie, where we use cotton labels.

HANGERS TO RECYCLING

EVERY YEAR WE BUY about 12 million hangers in recycled plastic. They are reused time after time in the stores and when they finally break we mend them or send them for recycling. Last year we sent almost 50,000 hangers to be mended and more than four million to recycling. The recycled plastic is used to make new hangers.

CONSUMPTION

When the garments leave our stores or are bought online they start their lives as part of our customers' daily life, but our commitment continues. We provide information about sustainable clothing care and offer textile collectings to extend the lives of garments and create conditions for more sustainable consumption.

THE AVERAGE CUSTOMER uses garments for 2.2 years, according to WRAP*. If we could extend the period of use by just three months, a garment's footprint in terms of carbon dioxide emissions, water consumption and waste would be 5-10 per cent lower than today. We therefore endeavour to design clothes on average that work for several seasons, but also to pass on knowledge on how customers themselves can contribute.

When the garments are no longer used, and it's time for something new, we want them to be taken care of in a constructive way. Our textile collecting *Wear, Love and Give Back*, is our answer to this. Through the collection we contribute to circular development and save useable textiles from becoming household waste.

*WRAP, Valuing our clothes – The true cost of how we design, use and dispose of clothing in the UK, 2012.

CONSUMPTION
23.5% of KappAhl's total climate impact

23.5%

CHALLENGES

- » Contributing to sustainable consumption, where products are produced and used in a more sustainable way.
- » The consumer often lacks sufficient knowledge of sustainable clothing care.
- » There is no large-scale technology for closing the circle for textiles and recycling more.

OPPORTUNITIES

- » Better management of resources and finances, thanks among other things to resource efficiency and recycling.
- » Increased accuracy and loyalty in relation to the customer.
- » Perceived as a long-term attractive and trustworthy fashion chain.
- » Inspire customers concerning clothing care and textile collecting to reduce the impact of the products.

IMPORTANT EVENTS DURING THE YEAR

Launched our textile collecting *Wear, Love and Give Back* in Norway and Finland • Continued focus on clothing care • Joined the research initiative Mistra Future Fashion

SMART CLOTHING CARE

WE WANT TO GIVE OUR WARDROBE HEROES the care they deserve, don't we? By avoiding washing clothes too often, washing at lower temperatures and not tumble drying them, garments have a longer life and their climate impact is reduced. Win-win!

All KappAhl's garments carry a Clever Care label and more information can be found on the clevercare.info website on how to best take care of your clothes. You can also find more information on clothing care in our Wash Right brochure on our website.

OUR CUSTOMERS HAVE THEIR SAY

THIS YEAR we conducted two customer surveys to find out what our customers think is important when they buy clothes, but also what they think about our sustainability work. Most important for our customers as regards sustainability is that KappAhl reduces the use of chemicals and waste, increases re-use and recycling of textiles and quality, and ensures that our production is based on good social and environmental conditions.

SAFE PRODUCTS

AS PART of our product safety work, on a few occasions during the year we decided to remove products from stores. One example is a kid's swim shorts where the inner lining was of poor quality.

128

TONNES OF TEXTILES
COLLECTED

PARTNERSHIPS FOR A CIRCULAR FASHION INDUSTRY

WE BELONG TO the Swedish Trade Federation's network Textiles for Recycling Initiative (T4RI), where we, together with other importers of textiles, promote better management of textile waste in Sweden.

We have also joined phase two of the Mistra Future Fashion programme that aims to create conditions for a circular economy in the fashion industry.

APPRECIATED TEXTILE COLLECTING

A CONSUMER throws away on average eight kilos of textiles as household garbage every year*. More than 95 per cent of these textiles could have a new life if we donated them to textile collectings instead. Therefore, in January 2015 KappAhl launched its Wear, Love and Give Back textile collecting in Sweden. In autumn 2015 the programme was launched in Norway and Finland and in December 2016 the programme will be rolled out in Poland as well.

Textile collecting is KappAhl's way of drawing attention to this important issue and it is highly appreciated by our customers. In the 2015/2016 financial year we collected 128 tonnes of clothes and home textiles. The textiles are sent to our partner I:Collect for sorting by quality to optimise reuse and recycling. The majority, up to 60 per cent, is re-sold as is to new owners. The textiles that cannot be reused are made into new material, such as

insulation. I:Collect also contributes to research and works to create new, high quality material from recycled textiles.

The customers receive a voucher to use next time they shop at KappAhl for every bag of used textiles they donate.

COLLECTED TEXTILES BECAME NEW SEWING MACHINES

For every kilo of textiles collected, KappAhl donates money to charity. In 2015 this amounted to more than EUR 1 600 from the textile collecting to our training centre for vulnerable women in Dhaka. They used the money to buy more advanced sewing machines, which meant the seamstresses can raise their skills level and thus increase their employability.

* Based on the behaviour of Swedes and SMED's studies for NVV.

THIS IS KAPPAHL

OUR VISION

KappAhl is to be a significant fashion chain in northern Europe.

OUR CORPORATE VALUES

Team spirit

ENERGY

CREATIVITY

Clarity

Courage

OUR CUSTOMER

OUR CUSTOMER is the woman the prime of life and we know her well. We know that she appreciates clear concepts, good fit and seeks inspiration and guidance both in the store and online. She wants a warm reception and value-for-money clothes. It must be easy to find what she is looking

for, both in the store and online. She buys both for herself and for the rest of the family. It is also important for our customer that the clothes are sustainably produced and that they can have a long life through good quality and recycling.

OUR PRESENCE

SWEDEN

Net sales, SEK million:
2,666 (2,516)

Presence: 174 (167) stores and Shop Online, of which 4 Newbie Stores and 2 Hampton Republic 27 stores.

Average number of full-time positions (restated)*: 1,403 (1,417)

NORWAY

Net sales, SEK million:
1,216 (1,196)

Presence: 100 (100) stores and Shop Online, of which 1 Newbie Store

Average number of full-time positions (restated): 597 (601)

FINLAND

Net sales, SEK million:
559 (562)

Presence: 59 (61) stores and Shop Online

Average number of full-time positions (restated): 336 (356)

POLAND

Net sales, SEK million:
282 (314)

Number of stores: 35 (40) stores and Shop Online

Average number of full-time positions (restated): 336 (365)

COMPETITORS

Most fashion chains and stores, as well as eCommerce with a similar profile, both as regards the whole picture and parts of KappAhl's range.

* Apart from store staff also includes all employees at KappAhl's head office and distribution centre in Mölndal.

** Based on order value. Excluding production at agents and importers.

OUR BUSINESS CONCEPT

WE ARE A FULLY INTEGRATED FASHION CHAIN offering a good value range of our own design. Our products are manufactured at the best price in large volumes throughout the world. The supply chain, from production to customer, is through a highly effective logistics chain. Using effective customer communication we build brand awareness and loyalty as well as driving traffic to our stores. We meet our customers in inspiring self-selection stores in good locations and through Shop Online. Our drivers are a business-like approach, cost effectiveness and sustainability. All in all, this means that we can create a long-term attractive offer with wide appeal.

PRESENCE AND MARKET

KappAhl has stores in Sweden, Norway, Finland and Poland as well as Shop Online in all markets. Sweden is KappAhl's single largest market. The value of KappAhl's total market is about SEK 200 billion. In fashion retailing KappAhl competes with international and local chains, independent stores, fashion departments in department stores, supermarkets and sporting goods stores. Fashion also competes with other goods and services that make us feel good. These include travel, sport and beauty products.

DEVELOPMENT OF THE INDUSTRY

Today's world of fashion is increasingly global and fashion more similar overall. Development has favoured large fashion chains with control over the entire process from design and purchasing to sales. This means that the chains can meet new trends, purchasing patterns and customer requirements faster. Customers' interest in getting inspiration and shopping online continues to grow. This is a trend that the chains have the size, logistics and technology to meet effectively. Clear concepts create stability in a trend-sensitive fashion world. There are more trends now than before and they shift faster. In addition, consumers more often mix different styles of clothing, levels of fashion, quality and price. Sustainability linked to fashion has become an increasingly important issue for consumers and other stakeholders in recent years. This development influences fashion companies and contributes to new business models and opportunities to strengthen brands. We also see that boundaries between the physical and digital shopping experience are to an increasing extent being erased.

OUR BUSINESS PLAN

Our business plan, Clarity for the customer, is based on five target areas – coordinated concepts; sales and service; channel optimisation; communication and marketing and sustainability.

	FOCUS AREAS	INITIATIVES 2015/2016	INITIATIVES 2016/2017
COORDINATED CONCEPTS	The right garment, at the right time, coordinated for our customer's wardrobe.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A new Vice President Assortment & Design has been appointed. • Gradual clarifications in the range. • Drawn up criteria for sustainable fashion. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of tools for sustainable design. • Clearer fashion concepts all the way from design to store and online.
SALES AND SERVICE	A high performance sales and service organisation with extensive knowledge of customer and product.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New structure for central support out in the store organisation. • Sales and service training for all store staff. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of our allocation strategy. • Continued sales and service training. • Introduction of Click & Collect.
CHANNEL OPTIMISATION	Optimise and update stores depending on concept, space and location with Shop Online as the flagship store.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continued roll-out of the store concept For You in 19 stores. • Shop Online launched in Poland. • Opened three new Newbie, two new Hampton Republic 27 and seven new KappAhl stores. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implement the For You 2.0 store concept. • Continued testing of our stand-alone concept stores – Newbie Store and Hampton Republic 27. • Work of readjustment in Poland completed.
COMMUNICATION AND MARKETING	Strong brand and strong relation to our main customer, leading to increased percentage of full-price sales.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New campaign and discount strategy. • Launch of digital customer club with all membership management in app, in Sweden and Finland. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Launch of our new communication strategy Feel. • Launch of digital customer club in Poland.
SUSTAINABILITY	Sustainability is a target area in all parts of the organisation. The work is governed by our sustainability strategy.		

OUR SUSTAINABILITY STRATEGY

SUSTAINABILITY WORK AT KAPPAHL is directed by management and led by a central sustainability manager. It is carried out every day by sustainability coordinators throughout the organisation, but also by everyone working at KappAhl (See page 43 in Part 2 for organisation chart). Sustainability is integrated into our daily work through our sustainability strategy Future Friendly Fashion 2020 with nine objectives and 62 activities. The sustainability strategy is developed on the basis of challenges we see in our value chain, for example with the help of life cycle analyses, the UN Development Goals and research around the planetary boundaries. We here present some of our most important targets and how we have worked during the year. You can find the strategy and our targets in full on our website www.kappahl.com/sustainability.

	OBJECTIVES	EXAMPLES OF TARGETS	STATUS
FUTURE We want to contribute to a better future for our planet.	Strive for climate neutral operations	Only purchase renewable energy by 2015. Read more on page 41.	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Enable sustainable resource use in production	Extend the scope of the STWI and PaCT projects for cleaner production for suppliers and sub-contractors in India, Bangladesh and Turkey by 2018. Read more on page 30.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Strive for reuse and recycling	Offer textile collecting in all stores in 2016. Read more on page 43.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
FRIENDLY We create long-term relationships with customers, employees and suppliers	Promote socially sustainable development at our suppliers	Apply for membership of the Ethical Trading Initiative by 2016 to assure the quality of our social responsibility work. Read more on page 33.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Act openly and transparently to inspire our customers and employees	All employees are to receive training in sustainability. Read more on pages 15 and 25.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Strengthen the lives of people, especially women and children, in the communities where we operate	Every year we ensure that all women trained at our training centre in Dhaka are offered work at our suppliers. Read more on page 31.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
FASHION Value-for-money fashion with wide appeal that is responsibly produced.	Design for sustainability	Develop a method to measure our products' sustainability performance by 2016. Read more on page 20.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Contribute to an environment free from hazardous substances	Constantly develop our "No Risk" programme to avoid dangerous chemicals in our products. Read more on page 27.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Use only sustainable materials in our collections	100 per cent of all cotton we use in 2020 is to be sustainably produced, i.e. organic cotton, BCI cotton or recycled cotton. Read more on page 29.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

More information on sustainability work can be found in Part 2 of this report.

- TARGET FULFILLED
- WORK GOING ACCORDING TO PLAN
- TARGET NOT FULFILLED

OUR FINANCIAL TARGETS

OUR FINANCIAL TARGETS refer to growth, operating margin, interest-bearing net debt and dividend policy. You can read more below about the past year.

	TARGETS	OUTCOME	COMMENTS								
OPERATIVE TARGETS	KappAhl's growth is to be an average of 4 per cent over a business cycle.	GROWTH, % Target: 4% <table border="1"> <tr><th>Year</th><th>Growth (%)</th></tr> <tr><td>2013/2014</td><td>-0.2</td></tr> <tr><td>2014/2015</td><td>-3.3</td></tr> <tr><td>2015/2016</td><td>3.0</td></tr> </table>	Year	Growth (%)	2013/2014	-0.2	2014/2015	-3.3	2015/2016	3.0	During the financial year the trend has turned upwards.
	Year	Growth (%)									
2013/2014	-0.2										
2014/2015	-3.3										
2015/2016	3.0										
	The operating margin must be at least 10 per cent	OPERATING MARGIN, % Target: 10% <table border="1"> <tr><th>Year</th><th>Operating Margin (%)</th></tr> <tr><td>2013/2014</td><td>6.2</td></tr> <tr><td>2014/2015</td><td>4.5</td></tr> <tr><td>2015/2016</td><td>7.4</td></tr> </table>	Year	Operating Margin (%)	2013/2014	6.2	2014/2015	4.5	2015/2016	7.4	With the exception of the previous year the trend has been positive towards 10% since the 2011/2012 financial year.
Year	Operating Margin (%)										
2013/2014	6.2										
2014/2015	4.5										
2015/2016	7.4										
FINANCIAL TARGETS	Interest-bearing net debt is not to exceed, other than temporarily, 3 times EBITDA.	INTEREST BEARING NET DEBT, TIMES EBITDA Target: ≤3 <table border="1"> <tr><th>Year</th><th>Times EBITDA</th></tr> <tr><td>2013/2014</td><td>1</td></tr> <tr><td>2014/2015</td><td>0.8</td></tr> <tr><td>2015/2016</td><td>0.3</td></tr> </table>	Year	Times EBITDA	2013/2014	1	2014/2015	0.8	2015/2016	0.3	The current level is within the framework of the target by a good margin.
	Year	Times EBITDA									
2013/2014	1										
2014/2015	0.8										
2015/2016	0.3										
DIVIDEND POLICY	Dividend is to be 40-60 per cent of the profit after tax provided that the Group meets the financial targets above.	DIVIDEND, % OF PROFIT AFTER TAX Target: 40-60% <table border="1"> <tr><th>Year</th><th>% of Profit After Tax</th></tr> <tr><td>2013/2014</td><td>43.6</td></tr> <tr><td>2014/2015</td><td>51.7</td></tr> <tr><td>2015/2016</td><td>39.2</td></tr> </table>	Year	% of Profit After Tax	2013/2014	43.6	2014/2015	51.7	2015/2016	39.2	
Year	% of Profit After Tax										
2013/2014	43.6										
2014/2015	51.7										
2015/2016	39.2										

KAPPAHL SHARE PERFORMANCE

This year we celebrated ten years on the stock exchange. Since 23 February 2006 the KappAhl share has been listed on Nasdaq Stockholm, Mid Cap. The KappAhl share is included in the Nasdaq Stockholm Consumer Discretionary Index. During the financial year the market value of the share increased by 66.8 per cent. This can be compared with the Nasdaq Stockholm All-Share index that increased in value by 4.4 per cent and Nasdaq Stockholm General Retailers that decreased by 16.0 per cent in the same period. See page 2 of the annual report part 2 for more share information. It can be found at www.kappahl.com/ir

FIGURES IN SUMMARY

KEY FIGURES

	September–August 2015/2016	September–August 2014/2015	September–August 2013/2014	September–August 2012/2013	September–August 2011/2012
Net sales	4,723.6	4,588.2	4,742.9	4,750.9	4,586.8
Sales growth, %	3.0	-3.3	-0.2	3.6	-7.8
Operating profit (EBIT), SEK million	349.3	197.8	272.1	252.3	-64.7
Adjusted operating profit (EBIT), SEK million	349.3	207.5	295.1	202.3	53.2
Operating profit (EBITDA)	479.8	333.4	400.6	395.9	155.4
Adjusted operating profit (EBITDA), SEK million	479.8	342.8	423.6	345.9	273.3
Total depreciation/amortisation, SEK million	130.5	135.3	128.5	140.6	220.1
Gross margin %	61.8	60.1	60.8	59.2	56.7
Operating margin, %	7.4	4.3	5.7	5.3	-1.4
Adjusted operating margin, %	7.4	4.5	6.2	4.3	1.2
Interest coverage ratio (multiple)	35.1	9.0	4.0	2.9	0.39
Net interest-bearing liabilities, SEK million	144.2	282.3	460.0	660.9	1,672.6
Net interest-bearing liabilities/Adjusted EBITDA (multiple)	0.3	0.8	1.1	1.7	10.7
Equity-assets ratio, %	58.1	56.6	56.1	49.4	26.2
Equity per share, SEK	23.50	21.36	20.12	18.42	3.85
Equity per share after dilution, SEK	23.50	21.30	19.99	18.42	3.85
Cash flow from operating activities per share, SEK	3.94	4.75	4.60	3.06	0.68
Market price, SEK	42.70	25.90	38.30	38.34	6.40
Market value, SEK million	3,280.2	1,989.6	2,874.0	2,877.0	1,440.8
P/E ratio (multiple)	13.4	17.9	22.3	31.6	neg
Dividend yield, %	2.9	2.9	2.0	0.0	0.0
Market price/equity per share, %	182	82	188	208	166
Earnings per share, SEK	3.19	1.45	1.71	1.32	-5.30
Dividend per share, SEK (proposed 2015/2016)	1.25	0.75	0.75	0.00	0.00
Weighted average number of shares	76,820,380	76,296,003	75,040,000	68,474,000	42,272,533
Number of shares at close of period	76,820,380	76,820,380	75,040,000	75,040,000	225,120,000
Number of shares after dilution	76,820,380	76,296,003	75,522,814	75,040,000	225,120,000

CONSOLIDATED INCOME STATEMENT (SEK MILLION)

	September–August 2015/2016	September–August 2014/2015	September–August 2013/2014	September–August 2012/2013	September–August 2011/2012
Net sales	4,723.6	4,588.2	4,742.9	4,750.9	4,586.8
Cost of goods sold	-1,806.4	-1,831.9	-1,856.6	-1,937.1	-1,988.1
Gross profit	2,917.2	2,756.3	2,886.4	2,813.8	2,598.7
Selling expenses	-2,356.0	-2,384.8	-2,468.9	-2,486.8	-2,526.9
Administrative expenses	-211.9	-173.7	-145.4	-150.2	-136.5
Other operating income	-	-	-	75.5	-
Operating profit	349.3	197.8	272.1	252.3	-64.7
Adjusted operating profit	349.3	207.5	295.1	202.3	53.2
Financial income	1.2	0.7	0.4	0.1	0.3
Financial expenses	-10.1	-21.8	-68.1	-87.3	-165.9
Profit/loss before tax	340.5	176.7	204.4	165.1	-230.3
Taxes	-95.6	-65.3	-75.1	-74.0	6.0
Net profit/loss for the year	244.9	111.4	129.3	91.1	-224.3

NOTICE TO ATTEND THE ANNUAL GENERAL MEETING

THE ANNUAL GENERAL MEETING OF KAPPAHL AB (PUBL) will be held on Tuesday 6 December 2016 at 10.00 at KappAhl's head office in Mölndal, Sweden, Idrottsvägen 14.

RIGHT TO PARTICIPATE

Shareholders wishing to participate in the Annual General Meeting must be registered in the share register kept by Euroclear Sweden AB no later than Wednesday, 30 November 2016, and have given notice of their attendance and that of any advisers by the same date, preferably before 12.00, via email to stamma@kappahl.com. Notification of participation can also be given by telephone on +46 31 771 55 00 or by post to KappAhl AB, Annual General Meeting, P O Box 303, SE-431 24 Mölndal, Sweden.

The notification must state the name, address, telephone number, corporate or personal identity number and registered shareholding.

Any powers of attorney must be in writing and be submitted no later than, but preferably before, the Annual General Meeting. A natural person representing a legal person shall also submit a certified

copy of the certificate of registration. The period of validity of the power of attorney may be a maximum of five years from its date of issue. KappAhl will provide a form for a power of attorney on request and the form is also available from KappAhl's website www.kappahl.com/ir.

Shareholders whose shares are registered in the name of a nominee through a bank's trust department or a private securities dealer must temporarily register the shares in their own name to be entitled to participate in the Meeting. This temporary registration of ownership must have been completed by Wednesday 30 November 2016. This means that the shareholder must notify the nominee of this well in advance of that date.

A complete notice to attend the Annual General Meeting will be published separately and in accordance with the provisions of the Articles of Association.

We look forward to seeing you!

FINANCIAL CALENDAR

Annual General Meeting	6 December 2016
First quarter (Sep-Nov)	21 December 2016
Second quarter (Dec-Feb)	6 April 2017
Third quarter (March-May)	29 June, 2017
Fourth quarter (June-August)	12 October, 2017

KappAhl's annual report part I in Swedish and English will be sent to shareholders and other stakeholders who so request. An order can be made via www.kappahl.com/ir. Part 2 of KappAhl's Annual Report is available for download from the same place on the website.

An updated financial calendar is published regularly at www.kappahl.com/ir

HERE ARE THE FIGURES

Would you like to read part 2 of our annual report?

You will find it at www.kappahl.com/ir. There you will find the financial reporting, the corporate governance report and in-depth sustainability reporting.

KappAhl AB, PO Box 303, SE 431 24 Mölndal
Tel: +46 31 771 55 00
www.kappahl.com

Please contact us via the contact form at
www.kappahl.com/contact or
via info_se@kappahl.com

KappAhl